

SUYUQLIKNING O'TKAZUVCHAN QISMLI KANALDAGI OQIMI MASALASIGA KOMPLEKS O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYALAR NAZARIYASINI QO'LLASH.

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Masalani yechishga kompleks o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar nazariyasini usullarini qo'llaymiz. Tekislikdagi masalani parametrik ko'rinishida qaraymiz, bunda parametrik soha sifatida $\zeta = \xi + i\eta$ yuqori yarimtekislikni olamiz.

Masalani yechishda Jukovskiy usulini qo'llaymiz:

$$\omega = \ln \frac{V_0}{\bar{V}} = \tau + i\theta, \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda $\bar{V} = u - iv = |V| \cdot e^{-i\theta}$ - kompleks tezlik, θ - suyuqlik zarrachasi tezlik vektorining x o'qi bilan hosil qilgan burchagi. ω funksiyaning o'zgarish sohasini (ζ) yuqori yarimtekislikka akslantiruvchi $\omega(\zeta)$ uchun chegaraviy shartlarni yozamiz:

$$AB \text{ bo'ylab: } \eta = 0, \quad -\infty < \xi < -b, \quad Im \omega(\zeta) = 0,$$

$$BC \text{ bo'ylab: } \eta = 0, \quad -b < \xi < -c, \quad Re \omega = \ln \left(\frac{V_0}{\bar{V}} \right) = 0,$$

$$CD \text{ bo'ylab: } \eta = 0, \quad -c < \xi < 0, \quad Im \omega = -\beta\pi,$$

$$DK \text{ bo'ylab: } \eta = 0, \quad 0 < \xi < 1, \quad Im \omega(\zeta) = \theta_1,$$

$$KA \text{ bo'ylab: } \eta = 0, \quad 1 < \xi < \infty, \quad Im \omega = 0.$$

Bu yerda θ_1 burchak (1) orqali belgilanadi.

Endi $\omega_1(\zeta) = \frac{\omega(\zeta)}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}}$ analitik funksiyani kiritamiz va ushbu funksiya uchun chegaraviy shartlarga ega bo'lamiz:

1-rasm

2-rasm

$$AB: = 0, -\infty < \xi < -b, \operatorname{Im} \omega_1 = 0,$$

$$BC: = 0, -b < \xi < -c, \operatorname{Im} \omega_1 = 0,$$

$$CD: = 0, -c < \xi < 0, \operatorname{Im} \omega_1 = \frac{-\beta\pi}{\sqrt{\xi+b}\sqrt{\xi+c}},$$

$$DK: = 0, 0 < \xi < 1, \operatorname{Im} \omega_1 = \frac{\theta_1}{\sqrt{\xi+b}\sqrt{\xi+c}},$$

$$KA: \eta = 0, 1 < \xi < \infty, \operatorname{Im} \omega_1 = 0.$$

(ζ) yuqori yarimtekislikni haqiqiy o'q bo'ylab $\omega_1(\zeta)$ funksiyaning mavhum chegaraviy qiymatlari asosida Shvartsning integral formulasidan foydalansak [1]:

$$\omega_1(\zeta) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \operatorname{Im} \omega(t) \frac{dt}{t-\zeta}$$

Funksiyani butun sohada qurish mumkin.

U holda

$$\omega_1(\zeta) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[-\beta\pi \int_{-c}^0 \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t+b}\sqrt{t+c}\cdot(t-\zeta)} + \theta_1 \int_0^1 \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t+b}\sqrt{t+c}\cdot(t-\zeta)} \right] \quad (2)$$

$\int \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t+b}\sqrt{t+c}\cdot(t-\zeta)}$ integralni hisoblash uchun $\frac{1}{t-\zeta} = s$ belgilash kiritamiz:

$$t = \frac{1}{s} + \zeta; dt = -\frac{ds}{s^2}.$$

Bundan

$$I(t) = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)(t+b)} + \sqrt{(\zeta+b)(t+c)}}{\sqrt{t-\zeta}}.$$

$$I_1(-c, 0) = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \left\{ \ln \frac{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\zeta)}}}{\sqrt{-\zeta}} \frac{\sqrt{-c-\zeta}}{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{c+\zeta}} \right\} =$$

$$-\frac{2}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\zeta)}}}{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\zeta}},$$

$$I_1(0,1) = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \left\{ \ln \frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\zeta)+\sqrt{(b+\zeta)(c+1)}}}{\sqrt{1-\zeta}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{-\zeta}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\zeta}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\zeta}} \right\}.$$

$I_1(-c, 0), I_1(0,1)$ integrallarni (A) ifodaga qo'ysak,

$$\omega_1(\zeta) = -\frac{2\beta}{\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\zeta)}}}{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\zeta}}$$

$$-\frac{2\theta_1}{\pi\sqrt{\zeta+b}\sqrt{\zeta+c}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\zeta)+\sqrt{(b+\zeta)(c+1)}}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\zeta}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\zeta}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\zeta}}{\sqrt{\zeta-1}}$$

Bundan $\omega(\zeta)$ ni topamiz

$$\omega(\zeta) = \ln \left[\frac{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\zeta)}}}{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\zeta}} \right]^{2\beta} \left[\frac{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\zeta}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\zeta}}{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\zeta)+\sqrt{(b+\zeta)(c+1)}}} \frac{\sqrt{\zeta-1}}{\sqrt{\zeta}} \right]^{\frac{2\theta_1}{\pi}} \quad (3)$$

(3.4) ifodadan foydalanib, kompleks tezlikni aniqlaymiz:

$$\bar{V} = V_0 \left[\frac{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\zeta}}{\sqrt{(\zeta+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\zeta)}}} \right]^{2\beta}$$

$$\left[\frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\zeta)+\sqrt{(b+\zeta)(c+1)}}}{\sqrt{\zeta-1}} \frac{\sqrt{\zeta}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\zeta}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\zeta}} \right]^{\frac{2\theta_1}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

(3.7) дан каналнинг ўтказувчан қисми бўйлаб суюқлик зарралари тезликларининг тақсимотини аниқлаш мумкин:

DK бўйлаб, $\eta = 0, 0 < \xi < 1$:

$$\bar{V} = V_0 \left[\frac{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{(\xi+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\xi)}}} \right]^{2\beta}$$

$$\left[\frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\xi)+\sqrt{(b+\xi)(c+1)}}}{i\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\xi}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\xi}} \right]^{2\alpha}.$$

У ҳолда тезликнинг ташкил этувчилари

$$u = V_0 \left[\frac{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{(\xi+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\xi)}}} \right]^{2\beta}$$

$$\left[\frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\xi)+\sqrt{(b+\xi)(c+1)}}}{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\xi}+\sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\xi}} \right]^{2\alpha} \cos \alpha \pi,$$

$$v = V_0 \left[\frac{\sqrt{b-c}\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{(\xi+c)b+\sqrt{c(b+\xi)}}} \right]^{2\beta}$$

$$\left[\frac{\sqrt{(b+1)(c+\xi)} + \sqrt{(b+\xi)(c+1)}}{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{\sqrt{b}\sqrt{c+\xi} + \sqrt{c}\sqrt{b+\xi}} \right]^{2\alpha} \sin \alpha \pi.$$

Endi $W(\zeta)$ kompleks potensialni (ζ) yuqori yarimtekislikda aniqlaymiz.

Oqim sohasiga mos keluvchi parametrik (ζ) sohaning haqiqiy o'qida (kanalning o'tkazmaydigan qismida) tok(oqish) funksiyasi o'zgarmas $\psi \neq const$, ya'ni $Im \frac{dW}{d\zeta} = 0$. Kanalning o'tkazuvchan qismida esa $[0; 1]$ oraliqda $Im \frac{dW}{d\xi} = \frac{d\psi}{d\xi}$.

Yuqori yarimtekislik uchun Shvartsning integral formulasi yordamida $\frac{dW}{d\zeta}$

hosilani aniqlaymiz:

$$\frac{dW}{d\zeta} = \frac{dW_0}{d\zeta} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 \frac{d\psi}{dt} \cdot \frac{dt}{t-\zeta}. \quad (5)$$

$\eta = 0$, $\xi \in [0; 1]$ oraliqda Saxotskiy formulasidan foydalanib, quyidagini olish mumkin:

$$\varphi_\xi = \varphi_{0\xi} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 \frac{d\psi}{dt} \cdot \frac{dt}{t-\xi} \quad (6)$$

Bunda $\varphi_{0\xi} = \frac{q_A}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{\xi+b}$ - devorlari o'tkazmaydigan kanal uchun tezlik potensialidan ξ bo'yicha olingan hosila.

ψ_ξ noma'lum funksiyani aniqlash uchun kanalning o'tkazuvchan chegarasi DK bo'ylab oqim sohasi (z) va parametrik (ζ) sohaning chegaralaring moslik shartidan foydalanamiz[2]:

$$x_\xi = \frac{u\varphi_\xi - v\psi_\xi}{v^2}, \quad y_\xi = \frac{v\varphi_\xi + u\psi_\xi}{v^2},$$

Qaralayotgan kanalning o'tkazuvchan chegarasida quyidagi o'rinli:

$$\eta = 0, \quad \xi \in [0; 1] \text{ da } y_\xi = 0,$$

$$\varphi_\xi = -\frac{\cos \theta_1}{\sin \theta_1} \psi_\xi$$

φ_ξ ni (4) tenglamaga qo'yib, ψ_ξ noma'lum funksiyaga nisbatan chiziqli singulyar integral tenglama (SIU) olamiz:

$$\psi_\xi \cos \theta_1 + \frac{\sin \theta_1}{\pi} \int_0^1 \psi_t \frac{dt}{t-\xi} = -\varphi_{0\xi} \sin \theta_1 \quad (7)$$

Kanalning DK qismi uchun bir tekis o'tkazuvchanlik o'rinli bo'lsa, ya'ni tezlik vektorining qiyalik burchagi θ_1 o'zgarmas bo'lsa, u holda (7) SIUning yechimini Rimanning chegaraviy masalasiga keltirish mumkin:

$$\psi_\xi = f(\xi) \cos \theta_1 - \frac{\sin \theta_1}{\pi} f(\xi) Z(\xi) \int_0^1 \frac{1}{z(t)} \cdot \frac{dt}{t-\xi} \quad (8)$$

bu yerda:

$$f(\xi) = -\varphi_{0\xi} \sin \theta_1; \quad Z(\xi) = \exp \Gamma(\xi).$$

$\Gamma(\xi)$ funksiya quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$\Gamma(\xi) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_0^1 \ln \left[\frac{\cos \theta_1 - i \sin \theta_1}{\cos \theta_1 + i \sin \theta_1} \right] \cdot \frac{dt}{t-\xi} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \cdot (-2i\theta_1) \ln \left| \frac{1-\xi}{-\xi} \right| = \ln \left(\frac{\xi}{1-\xi} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}}.$$

U holda

$$z(\xi) = \left(\frac{\xi}{1-\xi} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}},$$

bu yerda $\theta_1 = \alpha\pi$, $0 < \alpha < \frac{1}{2}$.

$$I(\xi) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1-\xi}{\xi} \right)^{\alpha} \cdot \frac{dt}{t-\xi}$$

Natijada xisoblashlardan keyin ψ_{ξ} funksiyasi uchun quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\psi_{\xi} = -\frac{q_A}{\pi} \cdot \frac{\sin \theta_1}{\xi+b} \quad (9)$$

(3.9) tenglamadan φ_{ξ} ni aniqlash mumkin:

$$\varphi_{\xi} = \frac{q_A}{\pi} \cdot \frac{\cos \theta_1}{\xi+b} \left(\frac{\xi}{1-\xi} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} \quad (10)$$

Endi (8) va (9) ifodalardan foydalanib, $W(\zeta)$ kompleks potentsialdan (ζ) bo'yicha olingan hosilani aniqlaymiz:

$$\frac{dW}{d\zeta} = \frac{q_A}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{\zeta+b} \left(\frac{\zeta}{1-\zeta} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} \quad (11)$$

Kanalning o'tkazuvchan DK qismidan o'tuvchi suyuqlik miqdorini aniqlaymiz:

$$Q = \int_0^1 \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} d\xi = -\frac{q_A \sin \theta_1}{\pi} \int_0^1 \left(\frac{t}{1-t} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} \frac{dt}{t+b}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \left(\frac{t}{1-t} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} \frac{dt}{t+b} = -\frac{q_A \pi}{\sin \theta_1} \left[\left(\frac{b}{1-b} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} - 1 \right] \text{ ekanligini e'tiborga olsak,}$$

$$Q = q_A \left[1 - \left(\frac{b}{1-b} \right)^{\frac{\theta_1}{\pi}} \right] \quad (12)$$

(12) formula asosida kanalning o'tkazuvchan qismidan o'tuvchi suyuqlik miqdori tezlik vektorlarining x o'qi bilan hosil qilgan θ_1 burchakning har xil qiymatlari uchun grafik ko'rinishda aniqlandi.

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